

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Programs in Sarangani Province: Promotion of the Triple Bottom Line Framework of Sustainability

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs implemented by business organizations in Sarangani Province in the frame of Triple Bottom Line Framework of Sustainability – People, Planet, and Profit (3Ps). It employed the mixed method research design using sequential qualitative and quantitative survey-type techniques. It involved fifty-two (52) respondents from medium-sized and large companies. Findings show that the main CSR drivers were customer satisfaction and company reputation/image while the major barrier was the lack of support from top management. In terms of involvement, the companies made efforts to address social injustice; partnered with communities to provide financial assistance; promoted waste management, energy, and water conservation; and, ensured employee well-being. In terms of integrating corporate citizenship, the companies recognized the role of leaders as CSR champions; incorporated CSR policies and integrated CSR initiatives in program development; installed CSR in their operational systems, as well as enabled M&E mechanisms. In assessing CSR program implementation, the companies established safety protocols in the workplace; educated their employees and the communities on environmental protection; and, hired local people from host communities. On issues and challenges, financial constraint was cited as a major concern while the benefits were gained from the areas of environmental conservation and compliance to national and local laws. Hence, the study concluded that many business organizations in Sarangani have already taken 3Ps- anchored proactive steps through CSR to make valuable contributions for the continuous development of medium and large-scale enterprises. It is therefore recommended that business organizations should increase their CSR program focus on Gender Equality, develop more CSR champions, increase employee involvement in CSR initiatives, and further CSR efforts through increased funding, while the government should introduce strategic measures to further encourage more companies to undertake CSR.

Keywords: business organizations; people; planet; profit; sustainable development

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1.Introduction

Since the start of the industrial revolution in the 1970s, the world has seen the birth of more business organizations which has in turn led to the creation of companies – the conglomerates and multinational companies (MNCs) that we know today. These business organizations have since taken over the world of commerce and trade, changed the landscape of doing business, and in the process, became an integral part of many of the world’s economies spanning across continents – from North and South America, Europe, Australia, Africa, and Asia (Kordos & Vojtovic 2016). Through the years, business organizations have grown and

become an indelible presence in many parts of the world. In the Philippines, there are 1,017,187 registered corporations and partnerships operating in the country as of December 31, 2018 according to the Securities and Exchange Commission.

Corporate social responsibility emerged at the turn of the century, which centered on the growing awareness and concern of business leaders on the responses of their respective communities, as well as the sustainability of their environments (Hamidu, Haron, & Amran, 2015). It was a strategy for them to comply with regulatory requirements, uphold standards, build corporate reputation, as well as create customer loyalty – the end-goal being